

Activation of Cbx7 by HPV16 E7.

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E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of *Cbx7* by HPV16 HPV E7.

Citations

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